

Potential neurobiological links between social isolation and Alzheimer's disease risk

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Abstract

It is estimated that 40% of dementia cases could be prevented by modification of lifestyle factors that associate with disease risk. One of these potentially modifiable lifestyle factors is social isolation. In this review, we discuss what is known about associations between social isolation and Alzheimer's disease, the most common cause of dementia. This is particularly relevant in the time of the COVID-19 pandemic when social isolation has been enforced with potential emerging negative impacts on cognition. While there are neurobiological mechanisms emerging that may account for the observed epidemiological associations between social isolation and Alzheimer's disease, more fundamental research is needed to fully understand the brain changes induced by isolation that may make people vulnerable to disease.

KEYWORDS

Alzheimer's disease, COVID-19, social isolation, synapse

1 | INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia and has devastating effects on both the individual and family. With a struggle to find disease-modifying treatments, targeting of disease risk factors has become an important focus in order to reduce prevalence (Livingston et al., 2017).

One of these risk factors is social isolation, which has long been known to affect both physical and mental health (House, Landis, & Umberson, 1988). Individuals with stronger social relationships have a 50% increased likelihood of survival compared to those with poor social

relationships (Holt-Lunstad, Smith, & Layton, 2010). The magnitude of this effect is similar to stopping smoking and exceeds many well-established risk factors for mortality such as obesity, physical inactivity and drinking excess alcohol (Holt-Lunstad, Smith, & Layton, 2010).

Along with other health conditions, social isolation has been associated with an increased risk of developing AD and dementia as a whole. The recent Lancet Commission on dementia prevention, intervention, and care estimates that there would be a 4% reduction in dementia prevalence if social isolation were eliminated as a risk factor in later life (Livingston et al., 2020). This reduction is greater than combatting physical inactivity in later life

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(2%) and hypertension in midlife (2%), highlighting social isolation as a significant issue that deserves more focus in dementia prevention.

This review will discuss the current epidemiological and pathological evidence for establishing social isolation as a risk factor for AD and dementia as a whole. We highlight potential neuropsychological and neurobiological mechanisms that may underpin this association. It is important to note that this association is bidirectional, as early symptoms of dementia may also lead to social withdrawal and isolation.

Objective social isolation includes the lack of social networks and reduced engagement in social activities. It is important to distinguish this from perceived social isolation, which encompasses feelings of loneliness and inadequate social support (Cornwell & Waite, 2009). In this review, we will differentiate these concepts by using the terms objective social isolation and loneliness, reserving the term social isolation for when we are discussing both concepts as a whole. The concepts are linked, but it is important to remember that people can have a large social network and still feel lonely.

2 | ESTABLISHING SOCIAL ISOLATION AS A RISK FACTOR

2.1 | Epidemiological association

Analysis of epidemiological studies is beneficial in establishing risk factors for disease. Social isolation has been associated with increased dementia risk. However, the epidemiological evidence for this association can be inconsistent, potentially owing to the breadth of measures used to assess both objective social isolation and loneliness, along with varying measures of dementia.

Marital status is one measure often used to assess objective social isolation and is considered an important contributor to social engagement, with married individuals generally having more interpersonal contact than single people. Being single has been associated with increased dementia risk in various studies (Fratiglioni, Wang, Ericsson, Maytan, & Winblad, 2000; Rafnsson, Orrell, D'orsi, Hogervorst, & Steptoe, 2020; Sundström, Westerlund, & Kotyrlo, 2016; Sundström, Westerlund, Mousavi-Nasab, Adolfsson, & Nilsson, 2014) while others have failed to identify a link (Vidarsdottir et al., 2014). Additionally, associations may depend on whether individuals are life-long single, widowed, or divorced (Sommerlad, Ruegger, Singh-Manoux, Lewis, & Livingston, 2018; Sundström, Westerlund, Mousavi-Nasab, Adolfsson, & Nilsson, 2014). Systematic review and meta-analysis help address inconsistencies in the literature by amalgamating and

systematically assessing previous research to form more robust conclusions. A meta-analysis including 812,047 people worldwide found that not being married, either being single or widowed, was associated with an increased dementia risk, although there was not an increased risk in those who were divorced (Sommerlad, Ruegger, Singh-Manoux, Lewis, & Livingston, 2018).

Other indicators used to assess objective social isolation include social network size, social participation and engagement, living alone, and frequency of social interactions. There are some inconsistencies at the single study level, with some studies finding having a smaller social network size to be associated with increased dementia risk (Crooks, Lubben, Petitti, Little, & Chiu, 2008; James, Boyle, Buchman, Barnes, & Bennett, 2011; Saczynski et al., 2006), and others not (Amieva et al., 2010; Boyle, Buchman, Barnes, & Bennett, 2010). In a meta-analysis of epidemiological studies comprising a total of 2,370,452 participants, poor social engagement, including having a poor social network and being unmarried, were associated with an increased risk of dementia (Penninkilampi, Casey, Singh, & Brodaty, 2018). When only including studies of high quality in the meta-analysis, an increased dementia risk of 55% persisted (Penninkilampi, Casey, Singh, & Brodaty, 2018).

Longitudinal studies are valuable when assessing dementia as they enable individual changes in cognition to be tracked over time within a cohort. A meta-analysis of 19 longitudinal cohort studies found that low social participation, less frequent social contact and greater loneliness were associated with incident dementia, while the association between social network size and dementia was inconsistent (Kuiper et al., 2015).

Assessing whether social engagement is protective against dementia is valuable when establishing social isolation as a risk factor. The meta-analysis discussed above assessed whether social engagement acted as a protective factor against dementia and although they found a significant reduction in risk, the findings were influenced by high publication bias (Penninkilampi, Casey, Singh, & Brodaty, 2018). A UK-based study with 10,308 participants found that more frequent social contact, measured by the frequency of contact with non-cohabiting relatives and friends, at age 60 years, but not at age 50 or 70 years, was associated with lower risk of dementia over 28-year follow-up, suggesting that social contact during late middle age may also be important. Interestingly, this study found the association to be driven by contacts with friends rather than relatives (Sommerlad, Sabia, Singh-Manoux, Lewis, & Livingston, 2019). A systematic review and meta-analysis of 51 longitudinal cohort studies found that lower levels of objective social isolation, measured by a high engagement in social activity and large social

networks were associated with better cognitive function in later life (Evans, Martyr, Collins, Brayne, & Clare, 2019). This meta-analysis excluded studies that assessed dementia status, suggesting that the effects of social isolation may extend more generally to cognition, which may in turn contribute to dementia risk.

It is likely that different types of relationships have distinct impacts on dementia risk and that some may be more crucial than others. One large study established five different subdomains: being married, having support exchanges with coresident family members, having contact with friends, participating in community groups, and engaging in paid work, that were associated with reduced dementia incidence. The domains were added together to create a social relationship diversity score and the authors found a negative linear relationship between this score and incident dementia, suggesting that each social domain may make an independent contribution to protecting against dementia. Those with the highest social relationship diversity score were 46% less likely to develop late-onset dementia compared with those with the lowest score (Saito, Murata, Saito, Takeda, & Kondo, 2018).

When assessing social isolation and engagement, it is crucial to consider the quality and meaning of these social interactions as that is also likely to contribute to subsequent dementia risk (Amieva et al., 2010) and may help explain some of the discrepancies seen, for example, in social network size. For example, providing an individual with a sense of purpose has been shown to reduce AD risk (Boyle, Buchman, Barnes, & Bennett, 2010). Objective social isolation studies often take lack of social contact to be negative and more frequent social engagement to be positive. Assessing the association between loneliness, or perceived social isolation, and dementia can help elucidate the importance of having meaningful connections in reducing dementia risk. As with objective social isolation, there are many ways to assess loneliness, with some measures overlapping between the two. Different scales have been developed to assist in measuring loneliness. These often confer advantage over using a single question, such as 'Do you often feel lonely?', as they help to holistically capture each participant's experience in a standardised manner. One scale that has been rigorously validated for use in research is the De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale which entails 6 different questions covering both emotional loneliness (missing an intimate relationship) and social loneliness (missing a wider social network) (de Jong-Gierveld, 1987).

Penninkilampi, Casey, Singh, and Brodaty's (2018) meta-analysis found no significant association between loneliness and increased dementia risk (Penninkilampi, Casey, Singh, & Brodaty, 2018). However only four studies were included, with only one using an official loneliness

scale. Using a modified version of the De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale, this study found that lonely individuals were more than twice as likely to develop an AD-like dementia syndrome, even after controlling for objective social isolation level (Wilson et al., 2007). Another, more recent, meta-analysis has found loneliness to be associated with an increased risk of dementia (Lara et al., 2019). Interestingly, one study included in the analysis, with a large sample size, found the association between loneliness and increased risk of cognitive impairment to be reduced in magnitude after accounting for health-related activity limitations and objective social isolation (Luchetti et al., 2020), whilst another study found loneliness partly mediated the effects of objective social isolation on cognition (Yang et al., 2020). In summary, both objective and perceived social isolation are associated with an increased risk of developing dementia, both independently and together. This is important to note when assessing social isolation in future studies and when guiding interventions, as increasing social contact may not be enough if the relationships do not alleviate feelings of loneliness.

An important point to consider with these epidemiological studies is whether there may be any reverse causation bias. Since dementia has a long prodromal phase, the association between social isolation and dementia is likely bidirectional and will be discussed in more depth below. However, when evaluating social isolation as a risk factor, it is important for studies to minimise this bias as much as possible. One study was able to do this by measuring social contact for an average 15 years before dementia onset, which is likely to extend prior to any prodromal changes of dementia taking effect (Sommerlad, Sabia, Singh-Manoux, Lewis, & Livingston, 2019). Another study excluded any individuals that were diagnosed with dementia within the first 5 years and found that the association between loneliness and increased dementia risk persisted (Sundström, Adolfsson, Nordin, & Adolfsson, 2020).

Some epidemiological studies show an effect of objective social isolation and loneliness on AD specifically (Bennett, Schneider, Tang, Arnold, & Wilson, 2006; Helmer et al., 1999; Wilson et al., 2007). However, many epidemiological studies do not distinguish between AD and other types of dementia as it is difficult to do this within the clinical setting. The effect of social isolation may not be homogenous amongst all types of dementia. For example, low social support at work was associated with an increased dementia risk that was slightly higher for vascular dementia than for AD (Andel et al., 2012). On the other hand, when assessing the association between loneliness and dementia, there was an increased risk for dementia as a whole and AD but not for vascular dementia (Sundström, Adolfsson, Nordin, & Adolfsson, 2020). Furthermore, there

was an excess increased risk associated specifically with AD compared to non-AD for those that had never been married compared to those who were married or cohabitants (Helmer et al., 1999).

2.2 | Human pathology findings

Using experimental techniques such as immunohistochemistry in human post-mortem tissue and/or brain imaging in living patients can help overcome the challenge of dissociating the links between social isolation and AD specifically, rather than dementia as a whole.

AD pathology is characterised by the accumulation of amyloid-beta in extracellular plaques and hyperphosphorylated tau in intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) along with inflammation, neurodegeneration and synapse loss (Serrano-Pozo, Frosch, Masliah, & Hyman, 2011; Terry et al., 1991). Loneliness, as assessed with a modified version of the de Jong-Gierveld Loneliness Scale, was not associated with the number of plaques or NFTs in human AD post-mortem brain tissue (Wilson et al., 2007). Contrastingly, a study looking at amyloid-beta deposition on positron emission tomography (PET) imaging found that amyloid-beta burden was significantly associated with greater loneliness (Donovan et al., 2016). Increased tau pathology in the right entorhinal cortex on PET imaging was also significantly associated with greater loneliness in cognitively normal older adults (Uquillas et al., 2018). In addition, loneliness 5 years ante-mortem predicted significant up- and down-regulation of AD associated genes in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, even after controlling for cognitive decline and AD pathology (Canli et al., 2018). It is important to note that the directionality of these findings cannot be established.

When assessing the association between objective social isolation and AD pathology, cognitive function remained higher for participants with larger social network sizes amongst those with more severe levels of global AD pathology (Bennett, Schneider, Tang, Arnold, & Wilson, 2006). Even when assessing cognitively normal older adults, lower baseline social engagement was associated with greater cognitive decline in those with higher amyloid-beta levels on PET imaging across the longitudinal study (Biddle et al., 2019). These pathology findings strengthen the epidemiological association between social isolation and AD.

However, it is important to note that some hallmark AD pathological findings, such as amyloid-beta plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, do not always correlate well with the extent of cognitive decline, or clinical dementia. Instead, the strongest neurobiological correlate of

cognitive decline in AD is synapse loss (Terry et al., 1991). Testing whether socially isolated individuals have increased synapse loss or dysfunction, would be valuable to elucidate the role of isolation more directly within the clinical syndrome. A number of biomarkers, capable of measuring synaptic injury and loss, are now emerging (Colom-Cadena et al., 2020). These include PET ligands that label synapses in the living human brain (Chen et al., 2018; Finnema et al., 2016), and CSF biomarkers that signal the occurrence of synapse degeneration (Galasko et al., 2019).

A limitation of these human studies is that they mainly use data from aging projects that tend to have participants of higher socioeconomic status and education level, leading to an unrepresentative sample of the population. Importantly, many studies did incorporate confounding variables into their risk analysis, including age, sex, education level, and depression. However, other risk factors for AD and dementia may impact upon social interaction and physical and cognitive activities, such as a high body mass index, frailty, reduced physical function (Di Marco et al., 2014) along with baseline personality traits (Fratiglioni, Paillard-Borg, & Winblad, 2004).

2.3 | Social isolation worsens AD pathology in rodents

It is impossible to mimic all aspects and complexities of social isolation in rodents, especially perceived social isolation and feelings of loneliness. However, invoking social isolation in AD mouse models, by housing mice away from cage mates, provides useful information to supplement human findings. Social isolation in APP/PS1 and Tg2576 mice lead to increased plaque formation and worsened memory (Dong et al., 2004; Hsiao, Kuo, Chen, & Gean, 2012; Huang, Liang, Ke, Chang, & Hsieh-Li, 2011) and induced spatial memory deficits, tau hyperphosphorylation and reduced synaptic protein expression in Sprague-Dawley rats (Gong et al., 2017; Ren, Gong, Wang, Zhou, & Zhang, 2015). Other pathological features of AD were also worsened, including exacerbated hippocampal atrophy, synapse loss and glial neuro-inflammatory changes compared to non-socially isolated APP/PS1 mice (Huang et al., 2015). A recent study found increased AD pathology even when socially isolated 5xFAD mice were provided with a running wheel or enriched environment, highlighting that the effects of isolation stress surpass any effects caused by lack of exercise or cognitive stimulation (Peterman et al., 2020). This raises an important consideration for general animal studies and the housing conditions used, as many

experimental conditions include some form of environmental and social deprivation.

3 | POTENTIAL MECHANISTIC EXPLANATIONS

3.1 | Bidirectional association between social isolation and dementia

It is crucial to note the bidirectional nature of this association (Figure 1). It is unclear whether social isolation is a risk factor for dementia or part of a dementia prodrome. Behavioural and Psychological Symptoms of Dementia (BPSD) describe the noncognitive symptoms and behaviours occurring in patients (Cerejeira, Lagarto, & Mukaetova-Ladinska, 2012). Of which, social withdrawal and emotional disengagement are highly represented in AD and can be prevalent prior to a dementia diagnosis (Porcelli et al., 2019). It is difficult to distinguish social withdrawal from other symptoms that likely inter-connect, such as apathy and depression in AD.

Those diagnosed with a dementia syndrome experienced greater reduction in social engagement prior to and post diagnosis compared to those that did not develop dementia (Hackett, Steptoe, Cadar, & Fancourt, 2019). There are a few potential theories for how the development of AD and dementia as a whole may manifest in social isolation. Firstly, cognitive defects may lead to social withdrawal as the individual struggles to maintain social relationships. There are inconsistent findings regarding whether social cognitive function is impaired in AD, or whether any deficits reflect the general cognitive decline seen in AD. Synapse loss and neurodegeneration in an area affected early in AD, the entorhinal cortex, which is involved in the affiliation network, may lead to social and emotional detachment from other people, exacerbating social isolation (Porcelli et al., 2019).

Individuals with AD may no longer enjoy engaging in social activities due to a changed or compromised sense of self (Hackett, Steptoe, Cadar, & Fancourt, 2019). In addition, the stigma surrounding some of the symptoms of AD, namely cognitive dysfunction and altered social behaviours, may act as a barrier to social interaction. Changes to the individual's personality may also make it difficult for friends and family to maintain socialising.

3.2 | Neuropsychological mechanisms

Social isolation may influence the development of AD through several psychological and neurobiological mechanisms. The cognitive reserve hypothesis suggests that the brain employs pre-existing cognitive processing or enrolls compensatory pathways to cope with brain damage (Stern, 2012). Those with lower education and occupational attainment or decreased engagement in leisure activities are associated with a greater risk of developing AD (Scarmeas, Levy, Tang, Manly, & Stern, 2001; Stern et al., 1994) and are thought to have a lower cognitive reserve (Stern, 2012). Social isolation decreases cognitive stimulation, potentially resulting in lower cognitive reserve, hence increasing the risk of cognitive decline (Evans et al., 2018). As stated previously, for more severe levels of AD pathology, cognitive function remained higher for participants with larger network size (Bennett, Schneider, Tang, Arnold, & Wilson, 2006), supporting this hypothesis.

Social networks exert social control over the individual, encouraging them to engage in health-promoting behaviours and discouraging health-damaging behaviours (House, 2001). Hence, social isolation may lead to the individual neglecting their health and also decreased access to health resources (House, 2001). It may also take longer for a patient to present if they have poor social contact as they may not notice subtle cognitive changes themselves. Further protective effects of social networks involve stimulating positive mood and wellbeing

FIGURE 1 Bidirectional association of social isolation and dementia. Social isolation has been identified as a risk factor for dementia, but it is also crucial to note that early symptoms of dementia, in particular, behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia (BPSD) and cognitive deficits may lead to impairments in social functioning and patients isolating themselves further

(Di Marco et al., 2014) and providing a sense of purpose and fulfilment to the individual (Berkman, 2000). Decreased mental and physical health through these mechanisms may lead to an increased vulnerability to developing AD.

3.3 | Neurobiological mechanisms: An insight from rodent models

Modelling social isolation in mice has provided great insight into some of the neurobiological mechanisms that may underpin the association between social isolation and AD. This section will explore some of these mechanisms and highlight findings from relevant human studies.

One neurobiological mechanism that could contribute to social behaviours increasing brain resilience is the effect on brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), which is important for neurogenesis and synaptic plasticity. BDNF protects against cytotoxicity and synapse loss in both amyloid and tau rodent models of AD but does not alter amyloid plaque load or tau hyperphosphorylation level, suggesting it acts through an

independent pathway (Arancibia et al., 2008; Jiao et al., 2016; Nagahara et al., 2009; Nagahara et al., 2013).

In the early 2000s, we described an effect of BDNF in modulating the beneficial effects of environmental enrichment, including housing with other mice, in a mouse model of Huntington's disease (Spires et al., 2004). Decreased BDNF expression is observed in the hippocampus of socially isolated rodents (Murínová, Hlaváčová, Chmelová, & Riečanský, 2017), potentially due to alterations in epigenetic regulation (Li, Du, Shao, & Wang, 2016).

In a model of AD, increases in BDNF, and subsequent neurogenesis in the hippocampus, mediated co-housing rescue of memory impairment in socially isolated AD mice (Hsiao et al., 2017; Hsiao, Hung, Chen, & Gean, 2014). Therefore, decreased BDNF expression through social isolation, might play a role in the development or progression of AD through decreased neurogenesis and synaptic plasticity (Figure 2). Overexpression of BDNF, along with increased adult hippocampal neurogenesis mimicked exercise-induced improvements in cognition in an AD mouse model (Choi et al., 2018).

Reduced levels of BDNF in serum, cerebrospinal fluid and brain tissue (Jiao et al., 2016) along with reduced

FIGURE 2 Social isolation is associated with a significantly increased risk of dementia and AD. There are a few neurobiological mechanisms that may mediate this association. Social isolation decreases AMPA receptor expression, leading to synapse dysfunction and loss. Increased oxidative stress and HPA axis disruption seen in socially isolated mice contribute to key parts of AD pathogenesis including neuroinflammation, amyloid-beta, and tau deposition and neurodegeneration which link together as detailed in the diagram. Decreased BDNF levels are also observed, decreasing neurogenesis which is seen in AD pathology. Importantly, more data are needed to establish whether these putative biological links between social isolation and dementia are occurring in human brain

neurogenesis has also been implicated in AD patients (Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2019; Tobin et al., 2019), although the data are not conclusive as to whether neurogenesis plays a major role in pathophysiology. One study found that social isolation trended with lower serum BDNF levels in participants, with greater emotional support being associated with higher serum BDNF levels and a reduced dementia risk (Salinas et al., 2017). A potential role for BDNF in this process is also supported by the genetic finding that BDNF polymorphisms may modulate risk of AD and depression associated with AD (Borroni et al., 2009; Riemenschneider et al., 2002).

Another potential mechanistic mediator of social isolation contributing to disease risk is oxidative stress. Chronic social isolation has been found to increase oxidative stress in rodents (Schiavone et al., 2009) potentially through activation of microglia. Markers of oxidative stress are often found early in the AD disease process, and so oxidative stress is thought to be an important factor in AD pathogenesis, particularly through increasing amyloid-beta and tau pathology (Liu, Zhou, Ziegler, Dimitrion, & Zuo, 2017). Increased production of reactive oxygen species is also associated with mitochondrial dysfunction, DNA damage and impairment of synapses, among others (Huang, Zhang, & Chen, 2016). In socially isolated APP/PS1 mice, use of chronic antioxidant treatment reversed accelerated amyloid-beta pathology (Hsiao, Kuo, Chen, & Gean, 2012), suggesting that social isolation may worsen AD pathology through increased oxidative stress (Figure 2). However, clinical trials of antioxidants for AD have thus far been unsuccessful (Persson, Popescu, & Cedazo-Minguez, 2014), indicating either that mice are not modelling this aspect of the disease well, antioxidants may not be reaching the brain in sufficient quantity or getting to the correct cell types or organelles, or that oxidative stress plays an early role in pathogenesis that is not effective to target at later stages (Fernández, Ivanauskas, & Ribeiro, 2017).

Increasing evidence has shown AD pathophysiology involves immune mechanisms that are mediated by glial cells, such as microglia and astrocytes (Heneka et al., 2015). Increases in reactive astrocytes and microglia, often surrounding plaques, and generalised gliosis are now considered neuropathological hallmarks of AD (Serrano-Pozo, Frosch, Masliah, & Hyman, 2011). Although pathological protein accumulation triggers innate immune responses within the brain, neuroinflammation can also drive pathology. Indeed, many risk genes for late-onset AD are predominately expressed in glia, indicating a crucial role for inflammation in AD (Karch & Goate, 2015). Modulation of neuroinflammation may present another mechanism by which social isolation contributes to AD risk.

Social isolation has been found to both increase (Du Preez et al., 2021; Schiavone et al., 2009) and decrease (Du Preez et al., 2020) microglial immunoreactivity in rodents. Similar results have been observed for astrocytes, with both no changes in immunoreactivity (Schiavone et al., 2009) and increases (Du Preez et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2017) observed upon social isolation. While there are disparities in these findings, likely impacted by the use of different species and social isolation paradigms, social isolation appears to impact glial cell biology. In a study using an acute social isolation paradigm, increased expression of the inflammatory cytokines interleukin-6 and tumor necrosis factor-alpha were observed in the hippocampus of isolated rats, indicating that even short periods of isolation can upregulate neuro-inflammatory responses (Alshammari et al., 2020). Longer periods of social isolation have also been shown to alter the inflammatory environment (Krügel, Fischer, Bauer, Sack, & Himmerich, 2014). In humans, a meta-analysis of studies found better social support and integration were associated with lower levels of inflammation (Uchino et al., 2018). This is important when considering that heightened peripheral inflammation was associated with cognitive decline and hippocampal atrophy (Simpson et al., 2013; Sudheimer et al., 2014), both of which are pertinent to AD.

In response to acute neurological insults, such as cerebral ischaemia following cardiac arrest or stroke, social isolation has been observed to exacerbate the post-ischaemic inflammatory response in rodents (Gaudier-Diaz, Zhang, Haines, Zhou, & Devries, 2017; Karelina et al., 2009; Weil et al., 2008), suggesting isolation compromises brain recovery mechanisms. These detrimental effects have been linked to reductions in BDNF (O'keefe et al., 2014), highlighting the interconnectedness of the downstream effects of social isolation. In AD, a more chronic neurological insult, isolated APP/PS1 mice displayed increased astrocyte and microglial immunoreactivity around plaques, suggesting that social isolation exacerbates plaque-associated gliosis and impacts AD pathology (Huang et al., 2015). Microglia and astrocytes are crucial for synaptogenesis and synaptic maintenance and, in development, sculpt neuronal circuits (Chung et al., 2013; Paolicelli et al., 2011; Stevens et al., 2007). Recently, glia have been proposed to contribute to AD-related synapse loss through aberrantly pruning synapses (Dejanovic et al., 2018; Hong et al., 2016). Although it has been suggested that social isolation may impact this process (Du Preez et al., 2020), further studies are required to test this empirically.

Social isolation may also act as a risk factor for AD by impairing myelination (Huang et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2012), perhaps also through increased oxidative

stress (Cai & Xiao, 2016). The role of myelin and oligodendrocytes, another type of glial cell, in AD is becoming increasingly recognized (Papuć & Rejdak, 2020), stemming from an early observation that cortical areas myelinated last are the first to degenerate in AD (Braak & Braak, 1996). Decreased levels of myelin basic protein, and other components of myelin, and numbers of oligodendrocyte progenitors have been reported in studies of post-mortem AD brain tissue (Behrendt et al., 2013; Gagyi et al., 2012; Roher et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2004). Impairments in myelin contribute to neuronal dysfunction and cognitive decline, and repair of this damaged myelin, or remyelination, is important for preserving CNS function. Adult mice subjected to social isolation exhibited changes in prefrontal cortex oligodendrocytes at the transcriptional and ultrastructural level, and displayed impairments in adult myelination (Liu et al., 2012). In mice subjected to myelin depletion, social isolation severely impacted remyelination through modulating interleukin-6 levels (Makinodan et al., 2016), highlighting another mechanism by which social isolation and inflammation can act to increase AD risk.

Synapse loss is the strongest pathological correlate of cognitive decline in AD (Terry et al., 1991). Social isolation has been observed to decrease the surface expression of AMPA receptors in an AD mouse model (Hsiao, Chen, Chen, & Gean, 2011). In a different AD model, increased expression of collapsin response mediator protein 5 (CRMP5) decreased social interaction, potentially by altering GluA2 surface expression, and triggering endocytosis of AMPA receptors (Lin, Lin, Chen, Yang, & Hsiao, 2019). Inhibition of AMPA receptor endocytosis prevented long-term potentiation decay and reduced memory loss in a mouse model of AD, suggesting a role for decreased AMPA receptors in pathological memory loss (Dong et al., 2015), and a mechanism by which social isolation contributes to the cognitive symptoms of AD. Social isolation also decreased levels of a synaptic protein, responsible for modulating synaptic plasticity, in the hippocampus (Pereda-Pérez et al., 2013). The socially isolated female rodents were also found to have a deficit in contextual fear memory, a task that is dependent on the hippocampus, suggesting a mechanism through which social isolation may alter synaptic plasticity, potentially increasing vulnerability to synapse loss in AD.

Another potential neurobiological mechanism linking social isolation to AD pathogenesis is the stress hypothesis (Fratiglioni, Paillard-Borg, & Winblad, 2004). Using the Tg2576 mouse model, social isolation significantly increased corticosterone levels and amyloid plaque deposition (Dong et al., 2008). Social isolation may act as a chronic stressor, elevating the levels of cortisol and therefore causing hypothalamic pituitary adrenal (HPA) axis

dysfunction. Elevated cortisol is associated with worse cognitive function and increased risk of AD in humans (Ouanes & Popp, 2019). The administration of glucocorticoids in transgenic mice led to accelerated AD pathology, including amyloid-beta formation and tau accumulation, suggesting a role of HPA axis dysfunction within AD development (Ouanes & Popp, 2019). Elevated cortisol has been shown to worsen atrophy of the hippocampus (Dhikav & Anand, 2011), which is particularly vulnerable to HPA dysfunction since it contains a high density of glucocorticoid receptors (Dong & Csernansky, 2009).

The normal function of the HPA axis is to respond to stress and regulate the immune system. Therefore, disruption can lead to alteration of the immune environment further affecting AD pathology (Heneka et al., 2015). Additionally, hippocampal glucocorticoid receptor activation decreased BDNF expression, and elevated cortisol increased oxidative stress (Ouanes & Popp, 2019), linking HPA axis dysfunction to the above mechanisms (shown in Figure 2). Equally, oxidative stress can worsen HPA axis dysfunction (Friedler, Crapser, & McCullough, 2015), highlighting the interconnectedness of the mechanisms through which social isolation may increase the risk or progression of AD (Figure 2).

Increasing evidence points towards the involvement of multiple cell types in AD pathogenesis, each orchestrating a host of complex and interconnected downstream processes. This “cellular phase” of the disease ultimately results in chronic brain dyshomeostasis and the clinical AD syndrome (De Strooper & Karran, 2016; Henstridge, Hyman, & Spiess-Jones, 2019). Such global neurobiological frameworks for understanding AD pathogenesis provide an important and holistic model to delineate how complex environmental risk factors, like social isolation, impact upon multiple aspects of AD pathophysiology.

4 | COVID-19

The effects of social isolation on dementia risk are particularly important in 2020–2021, with many people around the world forced into lockdown by the COVID-19 pandemic. While necessary, quarantine measures have been associated with many negative psychosocial outcomes, including social isolation (Röhr et al., 2020). Self-isolation will disproportionately affect elderly individuals, many of whom have been shielding, who rely on social contact outside of the home, such as group activities, places of worship and voluntary services, and especially those who do not have close family or friends (Armitage & Nellums, 2020).

Stress and social isolation associated with COVID-19 negatively impacts mental health (Robb et al., 2020), especially in those with pre-existing mental health conditions, further increasing the risk of dementia development (O'Connor et al., 2020). Furthermore, the knowledge of increased vulnerability to COVID-19 posed to elderly people due to age, comorbidities and frailty is likely to increase uncertainty and fear of the pandemic in this age group (Soares, Silvestre, Lima, & De Almondes, 2020). Enforced quarantine and shielding measures also reduces access to exercise, increasing dementia risk further through physical inactivity (Brown, Kumar, Rajji, Pollock, & Mulsant, 2020). Those with BPSD may also experience more distressing symptoms during isolation making it difficult for caregivers (Soares, Silvestre, Lima, & De Almondes, 2020).

Physical isolation should not have to result in social isolation. However, many virtual strategies require access to technology that some individuals do not have. Introduction of the bubble system within the UK may help to relieve some isolated individuals; however, more schemes focusing on increasing social engagement in vulnerable individuals are needed in order to minimise the impact of COVID-19 on the development of dementia. It is important to support those and pay particular attention to individuals that were already at higher risk of experiencing social isolation or loneliness, such as those who are socioeconomically disadvantaged or in poor physical or mental health, along with minority ethnic communities and LGBTQ individuals (Douglas, Katikireddi, Taulbut, Mckee, & McCartney, 2020; Teuton, 2018). This is essential as not only may these groups be more vulnerable to experiencing social isolation as a result of the lockdown restrictions, but they may also be disproportionately impacted by the pandemic response (Douglas, Katikireddi, Taulbut, Mckee, & McCartney, 2020) and experience further health inequalities as a result.

There are also substantial neurological, neuropsychiatric, and cognitive complications emerging of COVID-19 infection itself that warrant further attention (Ellul et al., 2020; Lleó & Alcolea, 2020; Ritchie, Chan, & Watermeyer, 2020; Varatharaj et al., 2020). Neurological symptoms and cognitive dysfunction post COVID-19 infection may be caused through multiple interacting mechanisms such as direct CNS damage induced by the virus, systemic complications of SARS-CoV-2 outside of the CNS that can affect the brain and through the psychological stress of both social isolation and experiencing an acute illness (Ritchie, Chan, & Watermeyer, 2020).

5 | FUTURE INTERVENTIONS

Determining the positive impact that social engagement can have in reducing dementia risk and progression is vital in order to guide effective interventions. As discussed above good social engagement is protective against dementia risk, however this association needs formal prospective testing to prove any causation. The Finnish Geriatric Intervention Study to Prevent Cognitive Impairment and Disability (FINGER), a randomized controlled trial involving dietary, exercise and cognitive training components found significant improvement in cognitive scores (Ngandu et al., 2015). This trial involved group activities, but similar trials would be important to isolate the effect of social interaction. In one intervention arm of a randomised trial in China, social interaction, delivered through meeting as a group for an hour three times a week, was associated with increases in brain volume as well as with some cognitive improvements (Mortimer et al., 2012).

The Frome model consisted of implementing a compassionate community approach, combining medical and social interventions within the population of Frome. The interventions used can be summarised as patient identification, goal setting and care planning, enhancement of naturally occurring supportive networks and linkage to community resource. Across the study period of 4 years, they found that the model was associated with significantly reduced unplanned hospital admissions and decreased healthcare costs across the population of Frome. This model found a way to bring social connectedness into routine clinical practice and took a holistic approach to patient's needs, connecting them to infrastructure already present within the community (Abel et al., 2018). Evaluating whether a similar approach could reduce AD prevalence specifically would be valuable.

Determining the mechanisms through which social isolation may increase dementia risk and understanding how these interact with physical inactivity, depression and cognitive stimulation, will be important to create effective interventions. It is also important to consider whether inorganic social interaction taking place within a trial setting has the same effect as spontaneous, organic social engagement (Penninkilampi, Casey, Singh, & Brodaty, 2018) and to consider the quality and types of social relationships as discussed above. Adapting these interventions in line with current and future COVID-19 guidelines will pose additional challenges.

Being able to model all the complexities of human social isolation within animals will continue to remain a challenge in deciphering the neurobiological links between social isolation and AD. Social isolation

(i.e. single housing) in animal models is usually not purely an alteration of the social environment, as it often involves factors such as decreased complexity of the environment, loss of tactile stimulation, and increased metabolic demands of temperature maintenance (Kim & Kirkpatrick, 1996). Taking these factors into account when designing experiments will be important to try to isolate the effect of social isolation from other contributors.

Shifting from mouse models to rat models may be beneficial as rats are inherently more social animals compared to mice and therefore may be better suited to modelling social isolation (Ellenbroek & Youn, 2016). This may be assisted by the fact that it is becoming easier to genetically engineer and produce disease models in rats. Furthermore, improving the modelling of animal habitats may help to enhance our understanding. For example, the use of a “Habitat” in which a group of 50–60 animals are allowed to live together, better reflects their natural environment and social hierarchies (SFARI, 2020).

Research in nonhuman primates may offer further insight, considering that many primate species live in large and highly social groups and display well-established social interactions and behaviours. Indeed, previous work in marmosets identified that social isolation in young animals disrupted hippocampal neurogenesis (Cinini et al., 2014), while macaques exhibiting loneliness, delineated by low rates of social interaction and high threat sensitivity, exhibited perturbed peripheral immune responses (Cole et al., 2015). Further investigation in older nonhuman primates focusing on the impact of social isolation and/or loneliness on AD-related processes would be valuable.

6 | CONCLUSION

To conclude, both objective and perceived social isolation are associated with dementia. However, more research is needed to validate potential causal links between social isolation and the development of AD both in terms of large scale human prospective studies and carefully designed animal studies. To do this, the challenge of isolating the effect of social isolation from other social and physical factors must be overcome. Expanding upon the potential neurobiological mechanisms detailed in this review and translation from animal to human studies will help to understand the role of social isolation in the development of AD, and/or as a symptom of AD. With enough detailed knowledge, it is possible that enviromimetics could be designed in the future to counter the effects of social isolation on the brain and lower risk of dementia.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed to writing, revision, and figure design.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

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No new data were generated in writing this review.

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